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Formulation Development and Evaluation of Fast Dissolving Tablet Loperamide HCl

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p><i>Article history</i> Received 25 May 2011 Received in revised form 28 May 2011 Accepted 30 May 2011 Available online 30 May 2011</p> <p><i>Keywords</i> Loperamide HCL Opioid Superdisintegrants Crospovidone Sodium starch glycolate</p>	<p>Loperamide HCL is an opioid receptor agonist and acts on the mu opioid receptors in the myenteric plexus large intestines; it works specifically by decreasing the activity of the myenteric plexus which decreases the motility of the circular and longitudinal smooth muscles of the intestinal wall. Loperamide HCL is a synthetic anti-diarrheal indicated for the control and symptomatic relief of acute nonspecific diarrhea and of chronic diarrhea associated with inflammatory bowel disease. Loperamide HCL, fast dissolving tablets have been prepared by direct compression method by using kneading mixture of Loperamide HCl and Crospovidone, after incorporating superdisintegrants such as Ac-di sol, Sodium starch glycolate, in different concentrations. All the formulation were evaluated for the influence of disintegrants and their concentrations on the characteristics of fast dissolving tablets mainly in terms of disintegration time and dissolution rate. Tablets containing Ac-di-sol at high concentration showed better disintegration character (10 seconds) along with rapid release (97.3%). The concentration of the superdisintegrants had also an effect on disintegration time and in-vitro dissolution. The resulting tablets were also evaluated for its hardness, thickness, wetting time and water absorption ratio.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

Oral drug delivery has been known for decades as the most widely utilized route of administration among all the routes that have been explored for the systemic delivery of drugs via various pharmaceutical products of different dosage forms. The reason that the oral route achieved such popularity may be in part attributed to its ease of administration as well as the traditional belief that by oral administration the drug is as well absorbed as the food stuffs that are ingested daily.¹ Fast dissolving tablets (FDTs) are solid single-unit dosage forms that are placed in mouth, allowed to disperse/dissolve in the saliva without the need of water and provide a quick onset of action. Some drugs are absorbed from mouth, pharynx and esophagus as the saliva passes down into the stomach. In such cases, bioavailability of drug is significantly greater than those observed from conventional tablet dosage form. FDTs are appreciated by a significant segment of population, particularly children and elderly, which have difficulty in swallowing conventional tablets or capsules.^{2,3,4} Recent developments in technology have presented viable dosage alternatives for patients who may have difficulties in swallowing tablets or capsules. Conventional tablets and capsules administered with water may be inconvenient or impractical for other patients. In such conditions there is a requirement of fast disintegrating/dissolving tablets which can be administered without water. Such fast dissolving/disintegrating tablets (FDT) disperse rapidly to form a suspension or solution of the drug after mixing with saliva which is easily swallowed by the patients.⁵ A fast-dissolving drug delivery system, in most cases, is a tablet that dissolves or disintegrates in the oral cavity without the need of water or chewing. Most fast-dissolving delivery systems must include substances to mask the taste of the active ingredient. This masked active ingredient is then swallowed by the patient's saliva along with the soluble and insoluble excipients.^{6, 7} FDTs are prepared by various techniques, mainly direct compression, lyophilization and moulding. The simplicity and cost effectiveness of the direct compression process have positioned this technique as an attractive alternate to traditional granulation

Determination of flow properties¹⁰

technologies.⁸ Loperamide HCl is Anti-Diarrheal agent loperamide is absorbed rapidly, with peak plasma concentrations occurring within 4 hours. Because of extensive first-pass metabolism, and its plasma half-life is about 11 hours after an oral dose.⁹

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials: Loperamide HCl was obtained as gift sample from Titan Lab. Mahad, pune. Crospovidone, Croscarmellose sodium, Sodium starch glycolate, Avicel101, Lactose monohydrate and Magnesium stearate was procured from S.D Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India and all other chemicals / solvents used were of analytical grade.

METHODS:

Kneading Mixture:

Tablets containing Loperamide HCl-Crospovidone Kneading mixture were formulated by following kneading method:

1) Kneading method:

A mixture of Loperamide Hcl (2 mg) and Crospovidone (10 mg) in ratio 1:5 was wetted with water: isopropyl alcohol (1:1) and kneaded thoroughly for 30 minutes in a glass mortar. The paste formed was dried under vacuum for 24 hours. Dried powder was through sieve no. 60# and stored in a dessicator for further evaluation.

Procedure:

1. The tablets were prepared by direct compression method.
2. All the ingredients were passed through a sieve number 20 # prior to mixing.
3. Loperamide Hcl-Crospovidone Kneading mixture, Ac-di-sol, Sodium starch glycolate, Avicel, Mannitol, Lactose monohydrate was properly mixed for 30 min in a suitable container to obtain a uniform blend. The blend was further lubricated with Magnesium sterate and Talc for 5 minutes.
4. The blend was compressed into tablets in Cadmach Rotary Machine an average weight of 175 mg using 8 mm flat punch in a rotary tablet press.

The composition of each formulated tablets are shown in Table No-1

a) Bulk Density:

It is the ratio of total mass of powder to the bulk volume of powder. It was measured by pouring the weighed powder (passed through standard sieve # 20)

into a measuring cylinder and the initial volume was noted. This initial volume is called the bulk volume. From this, the bulk density is calculated according to

Table No. 1
Composition of formulation of fast dissolving tablet of Loperamide Hcl (mg)

Sr.No	Ingredients (mg)	Batch code							
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	Loperamide HCl (2mg)+Crospovidone(10 mg)Kneadingmixture	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
2	Sodium starchglycolate	3.5	7	10.5	14	--	--	--	--
3	Ac-di-sol	--	--	--	--	3.5	7	10.5	14
4	Avicel PH 101	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35
5	Mannitol	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	27
6	Lactose monohydrate	86.5	83	79.5	76	86.5	83	79.5	76
7	Magnesium sterate	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
8	Talc	2	2	2	2		2	2	2

formula mentioned below. It is expressed in g/ml and is given by

$$\text{Bulk density (D}_b\text{)} = M / V_0$$

Where,

M = mass of power taken, and

V₀ = untapped volume

b) Tapped density:

It is the ratio of total mass of powder to the tapped volume of powder to he tapped volume of powder.

The volume was measured by tapping the powder for 500 times. Then the tapping was done for 750 times and the tapped volume was noted if the difference between these two volumes is less than 2%. If it is more than 2%, tapping is continued for 1250 times and tapped volume was noted. Tapping was continued until the difference between successive volumes is less than 2% (in a bulk density apparatus).

It is expressed in g/ml and is given by

$$\text{Tapped density (D}_t\text{)} = M / V_f$$

Where,

M = Weight of the sample mass taken.

V_f = Tapped volume

c) Compressibility index:

The simplest way for measurement of powder flow is compressibility, an indication of ease with which a material can be induced to flow is given by Compressibility index (C.I.). it is expressed in percentage and given by

$$\text{Compressibility index (C.I.)} = [(D_t - D_b) / D_t] \times 100$$

Where, D_t = Tapped density D_b = Bulk density

d) Hausner's ratio

The tapped density and bulk density were measured and the Hausner's ratio was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = D_t / D_b$$

Where, D_t = Tapped density

D_b = Bulk density.

e) Angle of Repose (θ)

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by angle of repose, θ. It is an indicative of the flow properties of the powder. It is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of powder and the horizontal plane.

$$\tan \theta = h / r$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h / r)$$

Where, θ is the angle of repose

h is the height in cm

r is the radius in cm

The powder mixture was allowed to flow through the funnel fixed to stand at definite height (h). The angle of repose was then calculated by measuring the height and radius of the heap of powder formed. Care was taken to see that the powder particles slip and roll over each other through the sides of the funnel.

B. Infrared Spectroscopic Study:

Loperamide HCl, Excipient and their combination were analyzed by Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR Perkin Elmer 100s) by KBr pellet method. They are compressed under high pressure in a hydraulic press to form a transparent pellet. The pellet was scanned from 4000 to 400-1 in FTIR. the change in the obtained peaks of pure drug.

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL EVALUATION OF TABLET¹⁰

1. Thickness:

Six tablets were randomly selected and the thickness of each was measured by digital Vernier caliper. Mean and standard deviation were calculated.

2. Hardness:

The hardness of ten tablets was measured using Monsanto Hardness tester. Mean and standard deviation were computed. It is expressed in kg/cm².

3. Friability:

The friability of the tablets was determined using Veego Friabilator. Ten tablets were initially weighed and transferred into the Friabilator. The Friabilator was operated at 25 rpm for 4 min. After 4 min the tablets were weighed again. The % friability was then calculated using the formula:

Friability = (Weight loss) / (Weight of tablets before operation) X 100

4. Weight variation:

Twenty tablets were individually weighed and average weight was calculated. The individual weight was compared to the average weight. The tablets pass the test if not more than two tablets are outside the percentage limit and if no tablet differs by more than two times the percentage the percentage limit. The weight variation tolerance for uncoated tablets is as follows:

5. Disintegration test:

The disintegration test was carried out using USP Disintegration Test Apparatus type-II. Six tablets were placed individually in each tube of disintegration test apparatus and discs were placed over each tablet. Simulating saliva pH 6.8. was used as the medium maintained at 37°C + 0.5°C and the time taken for each tablet to disintegrate completely was recorded.

6. Wetting time:

A piece of tissue paper (12cm × 10.75cm) folded twice was placed in a Petri dish containing 10ml of buffer solution simulating saliva pH 6.8. A tablet was placed on the paper and the time taken for complete wetting was noted.

7. Drug content:

50 tablets were powdered in mortar and pestle. Accurately weighed quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 100 mg of drug was transferred into 100 ml of volumetric flask. To it, 0.01M HCl was added to make up the volume to 100 ml. The resulting solution was sonicated for 5 min. and then filter through 0.50 μ filter paper. Dilution were made with 0.01M HCl to obtained a solution containing 100 μg/ml of the drug the drug content was determined by measuring the absorbance of the resulting solution spectrophotometrically at 226 nm.

8. In-vitro dissolution study:

Dissolution study was carried out using USP dissolution test apparatus type II. The dissolution medium used was 900 ml of 0.01M HCl which was maintained at 37°C. The paddle speed was kept at 50 rpm throughout the study. Ten ml of samples was withdrawn at every 1,2,3,4,5,10,15,30. Min. interval and then 10 ml of fresh dissolution media maintained at the same temperature was replaced. The samples were analyzed spectrophotometrically at 226 nm using 0.01M HCl as blank. The raw dissolution data was analyzed for calculating the amount of drug released and percentage cumulative drug released at different time intervals.

RESULT AND DISSCUTION:

Fast dissolving Tablet is new drug delivery system with several advantages and clinical benefits such as ease of administration for patient who are mentally ill, disable and uncooperative. Rapid disintegration and dissolution, no necessity of water or chewing and ability to provide advantages of liquid medication in the form of solid dispersion. In present study, attempt

was made to prepare such a tablet of various drugs by using addition of super disintegrants technique. The drug was selected for the study from the category

A) Flow Properties of blend:

Eight formulations was prepared by using different excipient like Crospovidone, Sodium starch glycolate, Croscarmellose sodium, Avicel, Mannitol, Magnesium stearate and talc. blend of drug and excipient were evaluated for various parameters as follows.

1) Angle of Repose:

Angle of repose was found in the range of **25.8-29.5 (θ)** the results are given in Table No. 2

2) Bulk Density:

The bulk density of various granules blends were measured by graduated cylinder. The bulk density was found in the range **0.518-0.585 g/ml** the results are given in Table No. 2

3) Tapped Density:

The tapped density of various granules blends was determined by using measuring cylinder. The tapped density was found in the range **0.645-0.675 g/ml** the results are given in Table No.2

antidiarrheal on the basis of low dose and immediate action.

4) Compressibility Index and Hausner's Ratio:

The compressibility index and Hausner's ratio of various granules blends was calculated by using bulk density and tapped density data. The Compressibility Index was found in the range **13.33 -19.69 %** The Hausner's Ratio was found in the range **1.22 -1.24** the results are given in Table No. 2

The angle of repose of Seven batches were found below **30(θ)** which indicated the blend having **excellent flow property.**

The Compressibility Index and Hausner's ratio of all batches were calculated. On the basis of obtained values we can concluded that, the blend of batches F1- F8 will have **fair to passable.**

B) Evaluation of Loperamide Hydrochloride Fast Dissolving Tablets

The study effort to prepare Fast Dissolving Tablet of Loperamide Hcl by using solid dispersion and different excipient in different concentration. The prepared tablets were subjected to various physiochemical

Table No. 2
Flow properties of formulations (F1-F8)

Formulation code (g/ml)	Bulk Density (g/ml)	Tapped density	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose (θ)
F1	0.539	0.668	19.3	1.24	27.2
F2	0.585	0.675	13.33	1.22	29.5
F3	0.537	0.662	18.88	1.23	27.8
F4	0.541	0.668	19.01	1.24	26.4
F5	0.539	0.663	18.70	1.23	29.8
F6	0.521	0.645	19.22	1.24	26.7
F7	0.537	0.660	18.63	1.23	25.8
F8	0.518	0.645	19.69	1.24	28.3

Table No 3
Evaluation of fast dissolving tablets (F1-F8)

Formulation code	Weight variation (mg) ±	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Disintegration time (sec)	Cumulative % drug release	Drug content (%)	Wetting time(sec.)
F1	175.91 ±0.5	2.38-2.40	2.0-2.5	0.39	20	95.5	96.5	22
F2	176.25 ±0.7	2.37-2.40	2.0-2.5	0.42	18	96.4	100.8	20
F3	178.40 ±0.6	2.35-2.37	2.5-3.0	0.37	18	92.8	98.4	21
F4	175.00 ±0.9	2.43-2.45	2.0-2.5	0.33	16	94.2	100.5	17
F5	177.22 ±0.5	2.32-2.35	2.0-2.5	0.34	16	94.0	99.4	15
F6	175.80 ±0.4	2.40-2.42	2.0-2.5	0.36	14	95.5	101.4	13
F7	174.25 ±0.7	2.43-2.45	2.5-3.0	0.41	12	96.5	97.8	16
F8	176.84 ±0.4	2.35-2.37	2.0-2.5	0.31	10	97.3	99.6	15

Table No. 4
In vitro Dissolution Profile for F1-F4

Sr.No.	Time (min.)	Cumulative % drug release (F1)	Cumulative % drug release (F2)	Cumulative% drug release (F3)	Cumulative% drug release (F4)
1	1	5.2	5.5	5.7	5.9
2	2	9.6	11.2	11.9	12.1
3	3	15.0	16.9	17.4	18.3
4	4	21.1	22.7	23.1	23.6
5	5	25.3	26.2	27.2	27.9
6	10	45.1	44.2	46.5	47.1
7	15	65.1	65.8	67.9	69.5
8	30	92.8	94.2	96	96.4

Figure No.1
Comparative study on dissolution profile of
Batch F1-F4

Figure No.2
Comparative study on dissolution profile of
Batch F5-F8

Table No. 5
In vitro Dissolution Profile For F5-F8

Sr.No.	Time (min.)	Cumulative % drug release (F5)	Cumulative % drug release (F6)	Cumulative% drug release (F7)	Cumulative% drug release (F8)
1	1	5.6	6.2	6.6	6.9
2	2	11.4	11.9	12.2	12.8
3	3	15.7	16.1	16.9	17.4
4	4	20.9	21.9	22.2	24.2
5	5	25.8	27.4	30.4	32.8
6	10	43.1	43.9	44.8	45.6
7	15	64.1	65.8	67.0	69.7
8	30	94.8	95.5	96.5	97.3

All formulation were varied from **175.00-178.40 mg** with minimum standard deviation values indicate that the uniform distribution of excipients and drug in the tablets. The results are given in Table No.3

Thickness:-

The tablets from **2.35–2.45 mm** in thickness with minimum standard deviation values, it assumed that the tablets show uniformity in thickness. The results are given in Table No.3

Hardness:-

The hardness of the tablets was found to be **2–2.5 kg/cm²**. The hardness of fast dissolving tablet varied although compression force was constant. This may be due to the increased concentration of the excipient in formulations. the results are given in Table No.3

Friability:-

The friability of the tablets was found to be **0.31–0.42 %** the results are given in Table No.3

Drug content:-

Drug content in the tablets were the limit of **92.8–97.8-%** the results are given in Table No.3

In-Vitro Drug Release:

The in-vitro drug release profile of batch F1 to F8 are displayed in Table no 4 & 5 and figure 1 & 2. Results indicate that batch F8 shows best results in terms of drug release and wetting time. Ac-di-sol (croscarmellose sodium) proves to be better super disintegrant in comparison with Sodium starch glycolate and Avicel PH 101 (Microcrystalline cellulose).

CONCLUSION:

The kneading mixture of Loperamide HCl with Crospovidone was prepared in the weight ratio of drug to carrier as 1:5 by using kneading method. The dissolution study was carried out the Kneading mixtures. The formulation F8 containing Loperamide-Crospovidone (km) and croscarmellose sodium was found to be best among all the formulation batches. The order of enhancement of disintegration with various superdisintegrants was found to be croscarmellose > sodium starch glycolate. Formulation batch F8 Processes good disintegration and dissolution profile. On comparing with their respective batches. the prepared tablets are passing the entire quality control test viz, friability, disintegration and dissolution rate. Wetting time. Faster disintegration and dissolution of Loperamide Hcl FDT may give better therapy for the treatment of diarrhoea.

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